

A Diagnostic Efficacy of Ultrasonography and FNAC in Evaluating Thyroid Nodules: A Comparative Study

Balaram Prasad¹, S. K. Suman², Amit Kumar³

¹Senior Resident, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Science, Patna, Bihar, India

²Professor and HOD, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Science, Patna, Bihar, India

³Associate Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Science, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 15-02-2024 / Revised: 14-03-2024 / Accepted: 27-04-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Balaram Prasad

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to compare diagnostic efficacy of ultrasonography and FNAC in evaluating thyroid nodules.

Methods: The present study was prospective, observational study conducted at in the Department of Radiodiagnosis, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical science, Patna, Bihar, India for the period of 2 years. In present study total 100 patients were included.

Results: The average age of patients was 36 years. Most common age group was 21-30 years (36%), followed by age group 31-40 years (26%). 80% patients in our study were female. 83% cases were benign, while only 18% were malignant as per final cyto-pathological diagnosis. Whenever histopathology report was available, that report was considered in final cyto- pathological diagnosis. Colloid nodule (64%) was most common benign lesion, other were follicular adenoma (7%), Hashimoto's thyroiditis (5%), subacute thyroiditis (2%), cyst (4%). Most common malignancies were papillary carcinoma (10%) followed by follicular carcinoma (6%), medullary carcinoma (2%), anaplastic carcinoma (1%). Radiologically features were compared in accordance to cyto-pathological diagnosis. Most common feature for internal composition was solid (46%) and predominantly solid (21%). Most lesions were hyperechoic (54%), well defined margins (78%), with peripheral halo (76%), without calcification (73%), without vascularity (77%).

Conclusion: Ultrasound evaluation is non-invasive, readily available, relatively inexpensive and with good resolution it helps to detect non-palpable and clinically silent nodules. USG also guides for fine needle aspiration of suspicious nodules. USG-thyroid should be considered as a first step and as an investigation of choice in evaluation of thyroid nodule.

Keywords: FNAC thyroid, Thyroid imaging, Thyroid malignancy

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Introduction

Thyroid disorders are the second most common endocrine disorders in Nigeria with a prevalence of 1.6%. [1] Nodular thyroid diseases are relatively common and found in 3-7% of the population worldwide. [2] The primary goal of thyroid nodule evaluation is to determine if a nodule is malignant or benign and whether it will or will not require surgery. In contrast to the high prevalence of thyroid nodules, thyroid cancer is rare, as fewer than 7% of all nodules are malignant and it is critical that they be identified accurately. [3] The superficial location of the thyroid gland makes it suitable for high frequency sonography which is the imaging modality of choice. [4] The role of FNAC in

evaluating euthyroid patient with thyroid nodule cannot be overemphasized as it reduces the unnecessary thyroidectomy for patients with benign nodules. [5] However, the combination of insufficient access to pathologists and the variable standards of pathology in sub-Saharan Africa undoubtedly mean that a significant proportion of cancer patients are receiving untimely diagnosis. [6]

The majority (90%) of thyroid lesions are benign as malignancy occurs only 1 in 10 thyroid nodules. [7] Most of thyroid nodules need evaluation to diagnose and treat them at the early stage. A large number of invasive and non-invasive investigations like ultrasonogram (USG), fine needle aspiration

cytology and thyroid nuclear scan are available for evaluation of thyroid swellings. The purpose of USG and FNAC is to pick the patients having malignancy for surgical intervention. The majority of thyroid nodules are readily detected by high resolution ultrasound (HRUSG). [8-10] FNAC provides very conclusive information about thyroid lesions. The use of FNAC reduces the number of thyroidectomies by approximately 50%, roughly doubles the surgical yield of carcinoma and reduces the overall cost of medical care in these patients by 25%. [11,12] But there are limitations for both USG and FNAC in the diagnosis of thyroid malignancies and still there is a doubt which one is more efficacious. [13]

The aim of the present study was to compare diagnostic efficacy of ultrasonography and FNAC in evaluating thyroid nodules.

Materials and Methods

The present study was prospective, observational study conducted at in the Department of Radiodiagnosis, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical science, Patna, Bihar, India for the period of 2 years. In present study total 100 patients were included. Patients underwent ultrasonographic evaluation of the thyroid gland and detected to have thyroid nodule, were subjected to further evaluation with fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC). A written informed consent was obtained from all patients for participation in present study.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients in whom conclusive reports of FNAC and USG were present, willing to follow up and willing to participate were included in study.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients who were not evaluated with FNAC, or had inadequate or indeterminate FNAC reports, inconclusive USG report, not willing to follow up or not willing to participate were excluded from study.

Patients with diffusely enlarged glands with multiple nodules and no intervening normal parenchyma were classified as multinodular goitre were also excluded. A total of 106 patients were considered for the study, satisfying inclusion and exclusion criteria. All scans were performed on Ultrasound equipment using a high frequency 5–12 MHz probe. Patients who underwent surgical excision, specimen were sent for histologic evaluation. FNAC was done as an OPD procedure by pathologist. These ultrasonographic findings were tabulated and correlated with the final pathological diagnosis. The data thus obtained was entered into Microsoft Excel spreadsheet, and the sensitivity, specificity and accuracy for each of the findings were calculated.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of subjects by age and sex

Age groups in years	N	%
Less than 20	7	7
21-30	36	36
31-40	26	26
41-50	15	15
51-60	9	9
61-70	5	5
More than 70	2	2
Male	20	20
Female	80	80

The average age of patients was 36 years. Most common age group was 21-30 years (36%), followed by age group 31-40 years (26%). 80% patients in our study were female.

Table 2: Final cyto-pathological Diagnosis

Final Diagnosis (FNAC/ HPE)	N	%
Benign	82	82
Colloid Nodule	64	64
Follicular Adenoma	7	7
Hashimoto's Thyroiditis	5	5
Subacute Thyroiditis	2	2
Cyst	4	4
Malignant	18	18
Papillary Carcinoma	10	10
Follicular Carcinoma	6	6
Medullary Carcinoma	2	2

83% cases were benign, while only 18% were malignant as per final cyto-pathological diagnosis. Whenever histopathology report was available, that report was considered in final cyto-pathological diagnosis. Colloid nodule (64%) was most common benign lesion, other were follicular

adenoma (7%), Hashimoto's thyroiditis (5%), subacute thyroiditis (2%), cyst (4%). Most common malignancies were papillary carcinoma (10%) followed by follicular carcinoma (6%), medullary carcinoma (2%), anaplastic carcinoma (1%).

Table 3: Radiological features

USG features	Malignant	Benign	Total
Internal composition Solid	12	34	46
Predominantly solid	5	16	21
Predominantly cystic	1	12	13
Cystic	0	8	8
Honeycomb	0	12	12
Echogenicity			
Hyperechoic	4	50	54
Hypoechoic	14	22	36
Anechoic	0	10	10
Margins			
Well defined	4	74	78
Ill defined	14	8	22
Peripheral Halo			
Present	12	64	76
Absent	6	18	24
Calcification			
Present	14	13	27
Absent	4	69	73
Internal vascularity			
Present	14	9	23
Absent	4	73	77

Radiologically features were compared in accordance to cyto-pathological diagnosis. Most common feature for internal composition was solid (46%) and predominantly solid (21%). Most lesions were hyperechoic (54%), well defined margins (78%), with peripheral halo (76%), without

calcification (73%), without vascularity (77%). Malignancy was noted when combination of factors such as solid and predominantly solid internal composition, hypoechoic, ill-defined margins, with peripheral halo, with calcification, with vascularity were present.

Table 4: Diagnostic Test Statistics of USG and FNAC for evaluation of thyroid nodule

Diagnostics statistics	USG	FNAC
Sensitivity	92	95
Specificity	93	100
PPV	78	100
NPV	96	97
Accuracy	92	97

Statistically we compared diagnostic efficacy of USG and FNAC for evaluation of thyroid nodule. FNAC had sensitivity (95 %), specificity (100 %), PPV (100 %), NPV (97 %), accuracy (97 %) while USG had sensitivity (92 %), specificity (93 %), PPV (78 %), NPV (96 %), accuracy (92 %).

Discussion

Thyroid gland is the earliest to develop in the foetus. There is approximately 4-5% incidence of clinically apparent thyroid lesions in general population.¹⁴ The prevalence of thyroid nodules varies from 19 to 67% and increases with age, affecting about 50% of the

population older than 40 years of age.¹⁵ Thyroid nodules are more common in females than in males which is about four times. Thyroid lesions become vulnerable particularly in countries where iodine intake in diet is low.¹⁶

The average age of patients was 36 years. Most common age group was 21-30 years (36%), followed by age group 31-40 years (26%). The average age of patients and age distribution in our study was similar to that of the previous studies.¹⁷ 80% patients in our study were female. The categorization of thyroid nodules into benign and

malignant nodules by USG is very important as it helps in the further management of the patients with nodular thyroid disease. Ultrasound has become the first-line imaging modality for the evaluation of the thyroid gland due to excellent visualization of the thyroid parenchyma.¹⁸

83% cases were benign, while only 18% were malignant as per final cyto-pathological diagnosis. Whenever histopathology report was available, that report was considered in final cyto-

pathological diagnosis. Colloid nodule (64%) was most common benign lesion, other were follicular adenoma (7%), Hashimoto's thyroiditis (5%), subacute thyroiditis (2%), cyst (4%). Most common malignancies were papillary carcinoma (10%) followed by follicular carcinoma (6%), medullary carcinoma (2%), anaplastic carcinoma (1%). In a study by Bumiya and Roopa¹⁹, benign pathology was observed in 90% cases, amongst which the commonest was goitre (66%) patients. A nodule with relatively decreased in echotexture compared to the adjacent strap muscles of the neck is considered hypoechoic. The previous similar studies have revealed that most malignancies demonstrate a hypoechoic nodule, yet most hypoechoic nodules are benign in view of the high prevalence of benign lesions.²⁰ The peripheral halo is usually complete and thin. It is irregular, thick, and incomplete or absent in a malignant nodule and is thought to represent compressed normal tissue due to the rapid growth of the tumor.²¹

Radiologically features were compared in accordance to cyto-pathological diagnosis. Most common feature for internal composition was solid (46%) and predominantly solid (21%). Most lesions were hyperechoic (54%), well defined margins (78%), with peripheral halo (76%), without calcification (73%), without vascularity (77%). Malignancy was noted when combination of factors such as solid and predominantly solid internal composition, hypoechoic, ill-defined margins, with peripheral halo, with calcification, with vascularity were present. Statistically we compared diagnostic efficacy of USG and FNAC for evaluation of thyroid nodule. FNAC had sensitivity (95 %), specificity (100 %), PPV (100 %), NPV (97 %), accuracy (97 %) while USG had sensitivity (92 %), specificity (93 %), PPV (78 %), NPV (96 %), accuracy (92 %). Fine needle aspiration cytology appears to be a safe, reliable, accurate and cost-effective method which provides valuable information to assist in selection of patients with solitary thyroid nodules for surgery. FNAC also distinguishes the benign from malignant lesions quite effectively preoperatively, it has been proposed as a preoperative screening method of choice.²² Although needle biopsy can be performed easily, consistently obtaining adequate tissue and processing the specimens to achieve accurate

cytopathological interpretation requires expertise and experience.²³ FNAC specimens are classified as malignant, benign, indeterminate (suspicious for follicular or Hurthle cell neoplasm), or insufficient for diagnosis. The effectiveness of FNAB of solitary thyroid nodules may be improved with the use of ultrasound guidance rather than simple palpation.²⁴

Conclusion

Ultrasound evaluation is non-invasive, readily available, relatively inexpensive and with good resolution it helps to detect non-palpable and clinically silent nodules. USG also guides for fine needle aspiration of suspicious nodules. USG-thyroid should be considered as a first step and as an investigation of choice in evaluation of thyroid nodule.

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